

Self-Leadership as a Tool for Enhancing Performance at Workplace

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Abstract

Self-leadership is the foundation of any leadership development initiative. It helps in developing an understanding of who you are (self), what you can do (your ability) and the ability to influence your communication, emotions, and behavior on the path to reach your goal. It is also related to the greater insight of work satisfaction, effective work relationships, enhanced communication, quality management, and in terms of health outcomes, less work stress and greater perceived wellness. The purpose of this paper is not only to study how Self-Leadership helps to succeed and motivate team to improve themselves and increase their productivity but also to explore how it may help an individual to come out of the stress and maintain proper work- balance. Further the research intends to evaluate self-leadership as the most effective tool for enhancing one's performance at the workplace and how it further affects the performance of the team.

Keywords: Self- Leadership, Ability, Team performance, Low work - stress, Work outcome.

Introduction

Prior studies have identified many aspects of leadership by exploring how a superior and leader influence his followers. A different perspective was introduced to the management literature 39 years ago, which focused on how people manage and lead

themselves (Manz & Sims, 1980). Self-leadership approach proposes that even if the behaviour is often influenced by external forces such as leaders and people whereas actions are ultimately controlled by internal rather than external forces (Manz, 1986).

Later, in (2003) Pearce and Conger, developed an approach, which suggests that leadership is an activity that can be shared or distributed among members of a group or organization to increase the productivity of an organization (p. 2). The research was further expanded to examine the relationships between self and shared leadership in the terms of team-based knowledge work, presenting a model that links self-leadership and shared leadership as an important forerunner in creating knowledge in team-based environments (Bligh et al. 2006). Ultimately, self-leadership not only helps in effectively leading themselves but also helps in motivating the team to develop a sense of self which helps in increasing the productivity of the team. In general, self-leadership strategies are portrayed impressive for improving self-focus, goal-setting processes, goal valence and prominence, feedback process and work-related self-confidence or performance expectancies. This helps the individual in maintaining work balance and reduce work stress. Self-leadership is thus a concept that spreads over organizational levels and simultaneously toward the analysis of researches at the personal and group levels. Nevertheless, most research has not been done on self-leadership considering the multilevel effects of self-leadership. Thus,

we believe that some of the most interesting and novel findings of self-leadership, along with paths for future work, can be identified only by seeing the levels. It is to assess how internal control at one level affects the process of internal control at the second level, can provide unique perceptions. Till date, very few self-leadership researches have been conducted outside the western world.

Literature Review

In (1980), Manz & Sims introduced the concept of self-leadership. The research was further expanded to explain how behavior is influenced by external forces but actions are controlled by internal force (Manz & Sims, 1980). Prussia, Anderson & Manz in (1998) developed a model on direct and indirect effects of self-efficacy and self-leadership on employee's performance which stated training enhances the self-efficacy & work performance. Later, Pearce and Conger (2003) suggest that leadership is an activity that can be shared or distributed among group members to increase organizational productivity. Individuals who practice self-leadership would have more potential and creativity than that of who wouldn't (DiLiello & Houghton, 2006). Later, in same year Neck & Houghton proposed "*Self-leadership as a normative model of self-influence that operates within*

the framework of more descriptive and deductive theories like self-regulation & cognitive theory". Self-leadership is not invariably beneficial at team-level but at the individual level, it improves the work performance and attitude (Stewart, Courtright & Manz, 2011). In 2013, Mutalip carried out research which shows situational characteristics like stressful environment can control the relationship between self-leadership and individual traits. Carmeli, Meitar & Weisberg in their 2018 research says creativeness of an employee who practices self-leadership would be increased by using reward strategies and self-leadership is positively connected with innovative or creative behavior.

Self-leadership

Self-leadership is the foundation of any leadership development initiative. Therefore, to understand the concept of self-leadership we need to explore the meaning and requirement of leadership. Although the meaning of leadership has been framed in many ways, experts in this field have a common understanding on the definition of leadership, which is in the form of influencing, motivating and enabling others to contribute to the effectiveness and success of the organization (McShane & Von Glinow 2008). From this definition, influencing and motivating are such a

powerful tool for individuals to employ towards success. To understand, the need for leadership, we need to look in the quote said by Peter Drucker:

"Only three things happen naturally in organizations: friction, confusion, and underperformance. Everything else requires leadership."

As Drucker pointed out, we need leaders to lead or anarchy would be born within the organization. Leadership is more like parenting. Like children, followers also learn by looking at their leaders. True leaders not only lead others but they lead themselves first. It is important for an individual to know how he can lead himself before leading others.

If you're to create something powerful and important, you must at the very least be driven by an equally powerful inner force.(Holiday, 2017)

Self-leadership is defined as a process through which individuals influence themselves through the use of specific sets of practical and cognitive strategies to control their actions and to fulfil the desired results (Manz 1986; Manz & Neck 2004). Bryant, Kazan (2012) defined Self-leadership as a tool for developing an understanding of who you are (self), what you can do (your ability), where you are

coupling with the ability to influence your communication, emotions, and behaviour on the path to reach your goal. In simple words “*Self-leadership is the process by which you influence yourself to achieve your goals.*” The practice of self-leadership provides the leader with necessary self-direction and self-motivation to achieve the objectives of personal and organizational performance.

Self-leadership corresponds to the leadership capabilities of Self-Observation and Self-Management but most importantly self-leadership affects all aspect of your life, your career, your health, and your relationships. Self-leaders are self-motivated to take determined action. Therefore, they make better leaders, entrepreneurs, and team members.

The main strategies of Self- Leadership are Self- Regulation, Self- Reflection, and Self- Perspective.

1. *Self-regulation* is a behaviour-based strategy, which helps a person to enhance self-feelings to facilitate behaviour management, especially related to necessary but often unpleasant tasks. This includes self-observation, self- assessment, setting self-goals and self-cueing which focuses on individuals' awareness of how, why and when he engages in a specific behaviour. Such self-regulation is an essential first step towards changing or eliminating ineffective or unproductive behaviour (Manz& Neck, 2004). With accurate information about current behaviour and performance levels, individuals can set behaviour-change goals more effectively for themselves. Behaviour-Based self-leadership strategies are designed to encourage positive, desirable behaviour that leads to successful outcomes while restraining negative, undesirable behaviour that leads to unsuccessful outcomes.
2. *Self-reflection* is a constructive thought pattern-based strategy, designed to facilitate the pattern of creative ideas and habitual ways of thinking that can positively affect one’s performance. Constructive thought pattern-based strategies include identifying and replacing unfit beliefs and assumptions and practising mental vision and positive self-talk. An individual should first examine his thoughts patterns, confronting and replacing unfit irritation beliefs and assumptions with the help of more creative thought processes.
3. *Self-talk* is the way you talk to yourself or your inner voice that involves mental self-evaluation and reactions (Ellis, 1977). By carefully analyzing self-talk patterns, negative or pessimistic self-talk can be prevented and replaced with

more optimistic self-dialogues (Seligman, 1991). Leaders are becoming more aware that a positive self-discussion is a powerful tool to increase your self-confidence and prevent negative emotions. Those who can master positive self-talk are considered more confident, motivated and productive. Individuals who visualize the successful performance of activity before the actual performance are more likely to achieve successful results when faced with the actual task (Manz & Neck, 2004).

4. *Self- perspective* is a Natural reward strategy, which shows that people develop perspectives and opinions by looking at and observing their behaviour and according rewarded. Self-perception has to be close to the other person's reality. There are two basic natural reward strategies: the first involves the creating an environment that given task itself becomes naturally rewarding and the other strategy consists of shaping perceptive by analyzing one's behaviour while preventing unpleasant aspects of the task. This strategy is designed to help in creating a sense of competence and self-determination, which in turn increases the behaviour related performance.

Self-Leadership & Emotional Intelligence

Self-leadership approach proposes that even if the behaviour is often influenced by external forces such as leaders and people but actions are ultimately controlled by internal rather than external forces (Manz, 1986). To control one's actions, one should know and control his emotions. The unique quality of great leaders is not IQ or privilege or job title it's the EI (emotional intelligence). Emotional intelligence is an important personal difference that is related to self-leadership. According to Mayer, Salovey and Caruso, emotional intelligence can see, understand and regulate the feelings of our own or any other person (Mayer, Salovey and Caruso,2000).High emotional intelligence focuses on emotions, uses them, understands them and manages them, and these skills serve those favourable actions that are potentially "good" for themselves and others.Mayer, Salovey, and Caruso said, *"Emotional abilities occur along a continuum from those that are at a relatively lower level, in the sense of carrying out fundamental, discrete psychological functions, to those that are more developmentally complex and operate in the service of personal self-management and goals. Crucial among lower level, fundamental skills is the capacity to perceive emotions accurately. Higher level skills include, for example, the capacity to manage emotions properly."*

(American Psychologist, 2008.)

Emotional intelligence operates mainly within the two contexts: first in one's own emotional state and another about the emotional state of others. The emotional facility is the ability of emotions which helps to think in three ways: firstly, by indicating significant environmental changes, secondly by changing the mood that helps in seeing the situation in many different ways, thirdly by facilitating logic. Hitherto, Goleman and his colleagues have developed the most popular emotional intelligence model which consists of four distinct dimensions: two external and two internal.

These dimensions include:

External

- *Social awareness* is about being sensitive to the feelings of others.
- *Relationship management* is about influencing and shaping the emotions of others

Internal

- *Self-awareness* is about knowing and understanding one's own emotions
- *Self-management* is about effectively controlling one's feelings

However, self-leadership and EI both concentrate on the same processes of self-influence, *EI* is mainly concerned with the self-regulation of emotions whereas *self-leadership* focuses on the self-regulation of behaviour and thought process. Even so, emotions have a powerful ability to influence cognitive processes and behaviours, both self-leadership and EI affect each other. People higher EI can manage their emotions effectively and are most likely to be more effective in leading themselves. Besides, self-leadership skills such as self-observation, the establishment of self-goal, visualizing successful performances, and self-reward etc., will be helpful for people to increase their emotional intelligence. People with higher EI are better at connecting with their team and also able to understand the emotions of their team, which helps in increasing productivity and achieves a successful outcome. This understanding, balance and control of one's emotions also help to enable a work balance which helps in maintaining low-stress levels at the workplace.

Self-Leadership & Self-Control

By avoiding the short-term distractions and temptation we can achieve long-term satisfaction. The most important thing in the journey of reaching one's goal is not hard-work (intensity) but consistency and this

consistency will be attained by self-control. As you heard of a phrase “water cuts through a rock, not by its strength, but by its persistency” This consistency leads to success by clearing our doubts, fear and apathy as stated in the quote by Dan Millman, an American author:

“Willpower is the key to success. Successful people strive no matter what they feel by applying their will to overcome apathy, doubt or fear.”

Self-control clears one’s vision of what they want and what they don’t want. Self-control is one of the most essential aspects of self-leadership which helps the individual to stay focused, persistent and patient.

“I am, indeed, a king, because I know how to rule myself.”

In this quote, Pietro Aretino, an Italian author and playwright said he powerful because he knows how to rule himself (self-leadership). Indeed, willpower is a conscious and effortful regulation of self, by the self. Willpower is the ability to what one needs to do even if they don’t feel like doing it. Like muscles are strengthened by regular exercise, the mind is strengthened by regular self- control practice which may improve one’s will-power over time. In order, to practice self-control daily one

should push themselves beyond their comfort zone.

Self-Leadership: A Key to Employee Engagement

“When business owners focus solely on profitability, work becomes a noun instead of a verb.”-(Boggs, 2019)

Today, the job title for many leaders has merely become a source of money. After getting your desired job title, most of them lose their passion. Then, People lose their love for their jobs and "work" becomes a noun rather than a verb which result in very low engagement in work or business and after seeing these leaders, employees also lose their motivation. We cannot always depend on the leaders above us. Therefore, we have to start leading ourselves.

Lars Sudmann in his TED talk said: *"Good leadership begins with self-leadership."* This is already proven that to lead others we should effectively lead ourselves first. Self-leadership points to our awareness, strength and development opportunities. Self-leadership is our ability to deliberately manage our thoughts, feelings, and actions and motivate ourselves towards our chosen purpose. The concept of self- leadership is not only meant for leaders but anyone can

practice it. Self-leadership can improve our communication skills, emotional intelligence and most importantly our will-power by which we can able to connect with our co-workers and leaders' better.

The most famous model of leadership for employee engagement is transformational leadership. In 1973, James V. Downton proposes this concept which was later expanded by James Burns. Transformational leadership is a leadership style in which leaders empower, motivate and influence employees to innovate, which will help to grow and shape the success of the organization in future (Bass, 1985; Burns, 1978). Transformational leaders give meaning, purpose, and direction to the action activities of followers by prominent followers with enthusiasm, inspiration, charisma, inspiration and emotional attention (Bass, 1990; Harms & Crede, 2010). Apart from this, a transforming leader taps the insiders to induce followers to maximize positive results (Shamir, House, & Arthur, 1993). Transformational leadership has four dimensions that include *Inspirational Motivation*, *Idealized Influence*, *Intellectual Stimulation*, and *Individualized Consideration*.

Inspirational motivation refers to the capability of a leader who provides an inspirational vision for the future to promote

team spirit in the future and motivation through the creation and spread of a compelling vision (Avolio & Bass, 1999; Bass, 1985; Bass & Avolio, 1995; Shamir, 1991). The *idealistic influence* concerns the extent to which a leader is a charismatic role model, which leads the followers to follow and internalize their thoughts and values (Avolio & Bass, 1999; Bass, 1985; Bass & Avolio, 1995). The *intellectual stimulus* is the ability of a leader to stimulate and encourage the innovative and creative thinking of their followers. For such a leader, learning is a value and unfavorable situations are seen as opportunities to learn. Followers ask questions, think deeply about things and find out the best ways to accomplish their actions. (Avolio & Bass, 1999; Bass, 1985;1999; Bass & Avolio, 1995). Lastly, *individual consideration* addresses the real care of a leader for others, as demonstrated by leaders participating in the betterment of the followers and promotes personal relationships. The leader gives empathy and support, keeps the communication open and keeps the challenges in front of the followers. The followers have the desires and aspirations of self-development and internal motivation for their work (Bass & Avolio, 1995).

Transformational leadership refers to two-way processes between leaders and followers, under which leaders lead

followers to perform through the use of occasional rewards (Burns, 1978). There is an established reward structure where the incentives are tied to performance standards same like the self-reward system in self-leadership. In 1985, Bass claims that the transformational leaders are concerned with improving the performance, maintaining work-balance, decreasing resistance to specific actions and implementation of decisions etc. As an employee engagement tool, transformational leadership has already spread in all sectors of organizations, including governmental organizations.

Thought Self-leadership: Stress Buster

Today, every person in the race of life is straining the stress. Stress can cause changes in our body that affect our overall physical, mental, and emotional health and at times which becomes unavoidable. This indispensable stress becomes a major hindrance in the path of a goal or target set by a person. This not only affects their personal life but also their professional life. Thought self-leadership integral component of self-leadership which helps in reducing stress.

TSL model assumes that the person can control and manage their thoughts so that later behaviour and performance can be

influenced. In other words, thought self-leadership suggests that employees can influence or lead themselves to attain higher performance by using specific awareness strategies that include mental imagery, belief, and self-talk etc.

- *Mental imagery* is basic imagining the performance or result of a task before actually performing it (Manz, 1992). This strategy has a direct influence on the performance of a person. If a person imagines a positive outcome during mental imagination, then it will move towards positive results like high self-esteem and low-stress levels. If he visualizes the negative result, his mental ability will be affected in the same way, which will lead to high-stress level and low self-esteem.
- Epistemologically, "*belief*" to refer to personal views connected with true or false concepts and ideas. According to Ellis (1975) & Burns (1980), individuals should recognize and face their dysfunctional beliefs and should change them with more rational beliefs. These negative thoughts are based on common non adaptive assumptions and beliefs that are usually activated by potentially troubling situations (Stress). Burns (1980) suggests that negative beliefs can be altered by identifying them and then altering those beliefs in more rational

beliefs. Thus, employees can improve their goal performance when he alters the irrational beliefs with rational ones.

- The last strategy of TSL is *self-talk*, which is the way you talk to yourself. In simple words your inner voice. It is recommended as a self-effective tool useful for improving the individual dominance of employees and managers (Manz & Neck 1991). Ellis points out that self-statement corresponds to emotional status, which in turn affects behaviour and cognition. Consequently, an employee may be able to increase the performance of his goal by controlling his emotional state. A controlled emotional status can be obtained through the change of an employee's internal dialogue (Manz and Neck, 1991; Neck and Manz, 1992). Over time, creative self-talk should be made internally so that the employee learns to use it quietly in their mind, improve their perception of difficult situations such as organizational change.

Conclusion

The most important quality of a leader is his emotional intelligence and self-control. Leadership is the capacity to influence individuals to make things happen. A leader needs strong self-control (willpower) to lead others. In order, to develop that self-control,

he needs to practice self-leadership. There are many definitions of self-control given by researcher but most commonly used synonyms are will-power, self-discipline, determination. In simple words, self-control is the ability to resist short-term temptations to attain long-term goals. Meanwhile, the capacity to deliberately influence your own ideas and actions to accomplish your private goals or goals of an organization is self-leadership. People who are self-led mostly make their own choices and set personal goals. Leadership is the impact method and is most frequently cited in relation to serving, motivating and empowering others.

The above mentioned study suggests if every individual in a team practices self-leadership at personal level, it will not only increase the work performance of the that employee but it also effects the productivity of team. Practicing self-leadership will help not only in maintaining low stress work life, higher employee engagement, good communication among team and higher productivity. Today, every person in the race of life is straining the stress. Stress can cause changes in our body that affect our overall physical, mental, and emotional health and at times which becomes unavoidable. So, we should learn how to manage stress effectively. Stress has both positive as well as the negative effect on us. There are many management theories, most

clustered in four key theory groups including theories of traits, behavioral theories, theories of contingency, and theories of authority and impact. Generally speaking, leading others is the main focus of each of the prevalent management theories. However, minimal attention has been paid to self-leading. Self-leadership involves self-consciousness, self-setting objectives, self-honor, actively rejecting pessimism, and being the change, you want to see in the globe. Self-leadership corresponds to the leadership capabilities of self-observation and self-management but most importantly self-leadership affects all aspect of your life, your career, your health, and your relationships. Self-leaders are self-motivated to take determined action. Therefore, making themselves better leaders, entrepreneurs, and team members.

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